

Local varieties Malbhog, Pokikoli, Silguti, Gajep sali 1, and Sarusokua suffered 15-20% leaf damage (see table). Nonpreference for feeding may be the resistance mechanism in these varieties. This study confirmed that glutinous rice varieties are less preferred by hispa. ■

Resistance of selected rice varieties to brown planthopper (BPH) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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The important rice pests in China—BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål and WBPH *Sogatellafurcifera* Horváth—usually occur together. Many varieties resistant to planthoppers have been released, and the threat of BPH and WBPH outbreaks significantly reduced. We evaluated damage, fecundity, and population dynamics of BPH and WBPH on some widely cultivated rice varieties, using the seedling screening technique in the glasshouse.

Xu-Shui 620 and Bing 664 were resistant to BPH but moderately resistant and moderately susceptible, respectively, to WBPH. Shan-You No. 6 was resistant to BPH but susceptible to WBPH. Both Shan-You 63 and Xiu-Shui 48 were susceptible to both BPH and WBPH.

In the ovipositing test, a pair of newly emerged BPH or WBPH adults were

Population dynamics of the brown planthopper (BPH) and the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) on select on rice varieties in ricefields, Hangzhou, China, 1990.

introduced into test tubes containing one plant of a variety. Plants were replaced every 2 d and the number of eggs laid counted.

At tillering and booting, the BPH female laid significantly more eggs on Shan-You 63 and Xiu-Shui 48 than on other varieties, but BPH fecundity at booting was higher than at tillering (see table). Shan-You No. 6, Shan-You 63, and Xiu-Shui 48 received more WBPH eggs than Bing 664 and Xiu-Shui 620 at tillering, but at booting, significantly fewer WBPH eggs were laid on all varieties.

In a field survey, Xiu-Shui 620, Shan-You No. 6, and Bing 664 had lower BPH populations than Shan-You 63, and Xiu-Shui 48. The number of BPH increased gradually with plant age, but the number of WBPH decreased rapidly with plant

age after 73 d old. This seems to be due to the decline in fecundity of WBPH after booting (see figure).

Japonica variety Xiu-Shui 620 appears to be most valuable as a BPH and WBPH resistance donor. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Rice genotypes with tolerance for low available phosphorus in Sierra Leone soils

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Soils in Sierra Leone are low activity clay type and low in available P. Inadequate P retards growth and development of rice. Identification of genotypes tolerant of low available P will assist breeders and farmers in minimizing adverse effects of P deficiency.

In 1989-90, we screened 294 local rice collected in 1988 for tolerance for low available P. In the uplands, 72 accessions of *O. glaberrima* and 72 of *O. sativa* were tested with and without P; in the inland valley swamp, 70 accessions of *O. glaberrima* and 80 of *O. sativa* were evaluated.

Damage and fecundity of BPH and WBPH on selected rice varieties.^a Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Variety	Damage rating ^b		Fecundity of BPH ^c (eggs/female in 8 d)		Fecundity of WBPH ^c (eggs/female in 8 d)	
	BPH	WBPH	Tillering	Booting	Tillering	Booting
Shan-You No. 6	1.3	9.0	51.2 bc	79.2 b	112.7 ab	92.8 a
Shan-You 63	8.7	9.0	74.5 b	139.9 a	138.6 a	86.0 a
Xiu-Shui 620	1.0	3.7	56.0 bc	78.5 b	77.4 b	69.9 a
Bing 664	2.3	5.7	34.9 c	62.9 b	82.7 b	74.6 a
XU-Shui 48	9.0	8.0	128.9 a	132.0 a	126.5 a	93.0 a
Rathu Heenati (resistant check)	1.0	1.3	22.4 c	28.6 c	12.4 c	10.1 b
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.0	9.0	113.2 ab	125.6 a	104.8 ab	88.4 a

^aSeparation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

^cAv of 2 replications.

Upland soil was sandy loam (Oxisol) with pH H₂O (1:1) 4.9, 4.3 kg Bray I's P/ha, 67 kg Bray I's K/ha, 105 kg total P/ha; 0.78% organic C, and CEC 10.2 meq/100 g. Inland valley swamp soil was clay loam (Typic Tropaquept) with pH H₂O (1:1) 4.2, 5.3 kg Bray I's P/ha, 74 kg Bray I's K/ha, 110 kg total P/ha, 2.4% organic C, and CEC 18.3 meq/100 g.

At the upland site, rice seeds were drilled 0.2 m apart in three 5-m-long rows/variety. At the inland valley swamp site, 21-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill, 0.15- × 0.20-m spacing, in three 5-m-long rows/variety. Fertilizer was 60 kg N as urea, 32 kg K as muriate of potash at the upland site, and 40 kg N and 32 kg K/ha on the inland valley swamp. P was applied at 25 kg/ha, as appropriate.

In the uplands, 30 *O. glaberrima* and 10 *O. sativa* varieties showed tolerance for low P; in the inland valley swamps, 20 *O. glaberrima* and 11 *O. sativa* accessions showed tolerance (Table 1). These results indicate *O. glaberrima*

Table 1. Rice germplasm materials tolerant of low available P in Sierra Leone.^a

Rice accessions	Upland				Inland valley swamp			
	T	MT	S	Total	T	MT	S	Total
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	30	20	20	72	20	20	30	70
<i>O. sativa</i>	10	15	47	72	11	18	51	80
Total	40	35	69	144	31	38	81	150

^aT = tolerant (90-100%), MT = moderately tolerant (80.90%), S = susceptible (less than 80%).

Table 2. Correlations between tolerance for low available P and some plant characters.^a

	Upland		Inland valley swamp	
	<i>O. gla.</i> ^b	<i>O. sat.</i> ^b	<i>O. gla.</i> ^c	<i>O. sat.</i> ^d
Tolerance vs				
a. tiller no. at maximum tillering	0.80**	0.75**	0.68**	0.62**
b. panicles/m ²	0.58**	0.49**	0.45**	0.40**
c. plant height	0.21 ns	0.23 ns	0.17 ns	0.22 ns
d. duration	-0.62**	-0.59**	-0.63**	-0.59**
e. panicle weight	0.66**	0.71**	0.59**	0.75**
f. phosphorus content in grains	0.72**	0.64**	0.48**	0.46**

^aSignificant at the 1% (**) level. ns = not significant. ^bn = 72. ^cn = 70. ^dn = 80.

varieties have greater tolerance for low available P than *O. sativa* varieties. These accessions will be used in breeding for tolerance for low available P.

Tolerance for low available P correlated significantly with tiller production, panicles/m², panicle weight, and days to 50% flowering (Table 2). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

VX-83, a promising very short-duration rice variety in Vietnam

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Very short-duration rice varieties are important for intensifying farming systems in Vietnam and expanding the areas of winter crops such as maize, sweet potato, soybean, potato, and vegetables.

In 1985 we used diallel crossing method to estimate the combining ability of some rice varieties and selected the promising cross-combination line 64-8-3. It matures in 95-100 d, has semidwarf stature, and is tolerant of lodging, drought, and submergence. It is a high-tillering plant type, with yields of 6-8 t/ha, 1,000-grain weight 27-28 g, resistance to major diseases and pests, and high grain quality. Line 64-8-3 was named as rice variety VX-83 and recommended for production.

VX-83 was selected from the cross IR8/IR22-XL//IR19746-11-33 (or CN2).

Performance of VX-83 in replicated yield trials at nine locations in 1988-89 is given in Table 1. VX-83 has the same duration as IR19746-11-33 and CN2 (check 2), and is about 18-22 d earlier

than IR8423 (check 1). VX-83 yields were higher than those of other entries. It has better resistance to major diseases and pests (Table 2).

VX-83 is recommended for late spring, early summer, and summer-autumn rice crops. ■

Table 1. Yields of VX-83 and other rices at 9 locations in 1988-89.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)								
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
IR8423 (check 1)	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.3	4.3	4.4	4.6	4.6	4.6
VX-83	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.4	4.3	4.5	4.6	4.6	4.6
C662083	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.1	4.0	4.0	4.4	4.4	4.4
IR19746-11-33 (check 2)	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.7	3.7	3.6	3.9	3.9	3.9

Table 2. Resistance of VX-83 to diseases and pests.

Entry	Reaction ^a to			
	Brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 2	Bacterial blight	Sheath blight	Blast
IR8423 (check 1)	1	2	7	5
VX-83	1	1	3	3
C662083	3	1	3	3
IR19746-11-33 (check 2)	1	2	7	5

^a1 = resistant, 3 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible.